

CLIMATE-CHANGE RESILIENCE INDICATORS FOR ENGINEERING INFRASTRUCTURE BASED ON CLIMATIC TUNNEL SIMULATION

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Riccardo Cacciotti, Arsenii Trush, Stanislav Pospíšil Institute of Theoretical and Applied Mechanics of the Czech Academy of Sciences, Prague, Czech Republic Abstract Climate change accelerates the degradation of the built environment, affecting material integrity and structural performance. With global projections anticipating intensified climate patterns, there is a pressing need for reliable risk assessment methods and climate-tailored, resilience-building measures. This paper presents an ongoing project, investigating the impact of climate change on key engineering infrastructure using wind tunnel simulations. The aim is to identify critical resilience parameters, damage functions and risk indicators. Activities include field measurements and observations, and laboratory work in the climatic tunnel to investigate climate phenomena and the response of building materials and structures.

1 INTRODUCTION

Natural and anthropogenic hazards, amplified by the effects of climate change, constantly subject the built and natural environments, especially key infrastructures, constructions, and urban settlements, to new pressures (Figure 1). Due to climate change, the frequency and magnitude of extreme climate events such as heavy precipitation, flooding, and drought will likely increase [1]. Projections of future heterogeneous climatic patterns impose additional, dynamic challenges and create an urgent need for innovative assessment methodologies and resilience-building measures, particularly for extreme climate situations. Although past research related to climatic modelling [2-4], vulnerability and safety assessment [5-6], and resilience-building measures has a solid foundation, there still are substantial gaps that need to be addressed in order to optimize the effectiveness of resilience building strategies. More specifically, the following aspects should be considered: (i) Climate factors will increasingly accelerate degradation processes and significantly harshen their impacts on the built environment. In this context, it is of primary importance to investigate, in depth, the effects of climatic conditions on building materials and to evaluate their performance under different scenarios. In particular, extensive and comprehensive sets of experimental data are required in order to improve the reliability of existing models in predicting the degradation of the esthetical, functional, and mechanical characteristics of building envelopes. The challenges requiring specific attention relate primarily to proper climate simulation procedures such as the reproduction of a homogeneous volume of rainwater per unit volume of air and the attainment of a raindrop size distribution similar to the one observed during real rainfall events. (ii) The variety of safety evaluation methodologies and the heterogeneity of definitions of vulnerability have been widely highlighted and demonstrated. Vulnerability ranking is a fundamental step for risk assessment and risk reduction. Input data used in risk management processes, e.g. in flood management, are often burdened with a range of uncertainties, which are subsequently reflected in the resulting design phase of solutions. Considering the societal importance of disaster protection measures and the associated financial costs for the implementation of said measures, the inclusion of uncertainty assessment in the risk management process is highly desirable. Risk analysis of key infrastructure, such as hydrotechnical and underground structures, has not yet been carried out in many countries, and a comprehensive international investigation of all underlying factors of

uncertainty, necessary for the creation of innovative solutions, is lacking. (iii) Research and innovation of user-driven solutions, tools, and mitigation and adaptation strategies based on sound scientific studies, capitalization of achieved knowledge, transfer and dissemination of results, and coordinated actions among the different actors involved in the decision-making processes for the protection and management, buildings, and sites (i.e. industry and governance sectors) is urgently required. In recent years, the drive to create solutions for strengthening the resistance of territorial units against global climate changes, natural disasters, social unrest, terrorist attacks, pandemics, military conflicts, cyber-attacks, and power outages is critical. Coping capacities for various unexpected dangers are part of urban resilience, and innovative research should focus on feasible solutions to economic, environmental, and social problems. In the perspective of implementing sound residence-building solutions, the issue of barriers in legislation, organizations, and management bodies must be addressed, in order to understand how measures can adapt to such challenges in the real-world applications. Such challenges are the focus of this paper and of the research work carried out within the framework of the INODIN project. Figure 1. October 2024: flooded infrastructure near Bologna (Italy), after heavy rain. Among other goals, INODIN investigates the critical parameters characterizing the resilience and sustainability of engineering infrastructures, providing advanced tools for performance-based design. In this perspective, it aims at gathering, processing and disseminating relevant data sets among the technical and non-technical actors involved in risk management from both the industry and governance sectors. The main scope is to provide optimized user-driven solutions, digitalized tools, and smart resilience-building strategies in the form of databases, recommendations, manuals and guidelines that could foster trans-sectoral cooperation and the development of application potential and would enable informed decision making in the field of civil engineering funding and planning.

2 WIND TUNNEL SIMULATION

For the sake of investigating key resilience indicators of engineering infrastructure under climate-induced scenarios, in addition to field observations, compatible laboratory methodologies can also ensure the collection of valuable data in a controlled environment. In this perspective, wind tunnel simulation is one the most promising and powerful tool available [7]. It permits determining the validity of experimental designs and theoretical models and evaluating the response of building materials to weather actions (e.g. rain, wind, and temperature) in terms of water absorption and penetration, drying, thermal transfer, as well as to understand the interaction construction-wind for the individuation of critical areas around the structure and finally to evaluate mitigating measures. In this research, the Vincenc Strouhal climatic tunnel is employed (Figure 2). It is located in the Centre of Excellence Telč, Czech Republic. The tunnel is a small-scale facility designed for civil engineering research, featuring a closed circuit with two sections: climatic and aerodynamic. The climatic section (2.5 × 3.9 m, 9 m long) focuses on building physics, material degradation, and cultural heritage protection. It can simulate weather conditions including wind (0.02–20 m/s), rain, snow, freeze, and radiant heat, with adjustable features like a spray rack for rain and an 8 kW infrared radiation system. The aerodynamic section (1.9 × 1.8 m, 11 m long) studies wind effects on structures and characteristics like pollutant dispersion, using turbulent elements and a turning table for model testing. Wind speeds here range from 0.06 to 50 m/s. Both sections can control airflow temperatures from –10 to + 40°C. The facility includes sensors for airflow diagnostics and environmental condition monitoring. For this research, only the climatic section is used Figure 2. Plan view of the Vincenc Strouhal climatic tunnel in Telč, Czech Republic 2.1 Rainfall simulation Simulating weather conditions in a laboratory requires control over several parameters, such as rainfall intensity, wind speed and direction, and temperature. For wind-driven rain, it is crucial to validate laboratory-generated rainfall data against field measurements to ensure realistic simulations. This approach enables the study of building materials' responses to combined wind and rain loads, their susceptibility to damage, and the evaluation of resilience building measures. In this research, rainfall is simulated in the climatic wind tunnel using the rain pulse method [8-9]. This

method discretizes natural rainfall into constant-intensity pulses, with varying intensities achieved by adjusting pulse density over time. Table 1 illustrates the tunnel input characteristics for a typical summer storm (3 hours average duration and 7.2mm total precipitation, based on statistical analysis of weather data for Prague, CZ). During such event, 85% of precipitation occurs as heavy rainfall in the initial minutes (15% of total duration), followed by a prolonged drizzle i.e. remaining 15% of rainfall over 85% of the event duration. In the tunnel, this is replicated with dense 1-minute pulses at fixed intensity during the early phase, transitioning to sparser pulses later. The constant-pulse approach simplifies the experimental protocol, maintaining consistent laboratory conditions, such as nozzle type, sprinkler configuration, and pressure. The rain simulation setup uses TG-2.8 W Unijet nozzles, six sprinklers with a 0.65 × 0.8 m grid, and a constant system pressure of 120 kPa. These parameters yield a simulated rain intensity of 36 mm/h, corresponding to very heavy rainfall. This rain intensity value represents the maximum achievable in the tunnel, using the set-up described above. Any other rainfall intensity below this maximum is simulated discretising the continuous rain, employing the pulse density method. Additional details on tunnel input parameters are discussed in [8].

Figure 3. Rainfall simulated in the tunnel. Evaluating the response of building materials to rain loads is crucial for identifying potential critical scenarios that may lead to damaging conditions. Such scenarios include excessive rain infiltration into deeper material layers, heightening risks of salt crystallization and freeze-thaw damage, or substantial surface run-off, which increases moisture exposure in lower areas. Figure 4 provides an example of possible measurements that can be carried out in the tunnel. For the summer storm event described above and presented in Table 1, the gravimetric method (obtained in this case by hanging masonry pillars to force transducers connected to a steel frame), return valuable information concerning the properties of the building component, its absorption and moisture storage capacity as well as its drying features. Such information, together with data from other simulations, enable characterising the scenario and individuating possible resilience building strategies that can be implemented to reduce the effects of climate-change induced actions. Figure 4. Gravimetric determination of water absorption during simulated rain (as per Table 1).

Table 1. Example of discretisation of rainfall event for tunnel inputs (total duration 180 min, total rainfall 7.2mm).

2.2 Aerodynamic tests

Aerodynamic testing in wind tunnels is pivotal in studying the behavior of buildings under controlled airflow conditions, providing detailed insights into aerodynamic forces, drag, lift, and flow patterns. Its scope extends to climate simulation by analyzing how structures interact with various wind conditions, including extreme weather scenarios influenced by climate change, enabling engineers to predict and optimize designs for energy efficiency, resilience, and minimal environmental impact. In this study, the simulation of various atmospheric boundary layer characteristics in the wind tunnel aims at investigating the exposure of building surfaces to different climate-induced mechanisms, such as for example, individuating the areas subjected to the highest rate of raindrop/particle deposition, the locations of potential erosion etc... Figure 5. Physical model ready for pressure measurement. In order to reach this goal, two methodologies are suggested: 1) pressure testing and 2) flow visualization. These are further discussed in the following sections. Extended details and discussion of results can be found in [10]

2.2.1 Pressure testing

This method involves testing physical models of real structures equipped with silicone tubes that connect strategically placed openings on the model to a dynamic pressure scanner (Figure 5). This setup enables highly accurate differential pressure measurements, with a range of 1245 Pa and a sensitivity of ±0.05%. The recorded pressure values are normalized to testing conditions using pressure coefficients, calculated with equation (1):

$$C_p = \frac{2(p_x - p_r)}{\rho U_{mean}^2} \quad (1)$$

where p_x is the measured pressure at a specific point; p_r is the static (barometric) pressure of undisturbed flow (measured using a Prandtl-Pitot tube); ρ is the air density and U_{mean} is the mean wind speed at the reference location. Models are placed on a turntable in the wind tunnel's aerodynamic section to measure pressures across various wind attack angles α , ranging from 0° to 360° in 15° increments. The differential pressure captured by the transducer represents the wind pressure at the measured point. The wind speed in the tunnel is not required to match real site conditions, as it primarily serves to establish dimensionless coefficients.

3 RESILIENCE INDICATORS AND RISK MITIGATION

Resilience indicators for engineering infrastructure are essential tools for assessing and enhancing the ability of systems to withstand, adapt to, and recover from disruptions. These indicators provide measurable parameters that capture various aspects of resilience, such as structural robustness, adaptability, and recovery efficiency. By integrating resilience metrics into the design, maintenance, and operation of infrastructure, engineers can identify vulnerabilities, prioritize resources, and implement strategies that ensure functionality is maintained or quickly restored after adverse events. This approach is essential for fostering sustainable and reliable infrastructure in the face of growing challenges such as climate change, natural disasters, and urbanization. Figure 8. Moisture monitoring in sandstone samples during rain penetration test in a laboratory-size wind tunnel. Results from testing as described in the previous section, provide fundamental experimental data for establishing those scenarios under Figure 9. Risk mitigation workflow. which constructions can be more sensitive to climate-induced damage. For example, monitoring of rainwater penetration into material allows individuating moisture content profiles along the cross-section of the material sample (Figure 8). By assuming the conditions of significant differentials in moisture content caused by rainwater penetration, for example, porous materials are more prone to experience damage at the interface between the 'wet' and 'dry' zones, especially when the synergic effects of multiple factors such as freezing temperatures and salts come into play. From this assumption, a sensitivity curve can be established by relating weather conditions (e.g. rain intensity) and the magnitude of moisture content differential between two adjacent zones, expressed as a normalized susceptibility indicator (Figure 10). Similarly, other experimentally measured parameters can be introduced to individuate a number of additional sensitivity indicators, necessary to appropriately describe the case under analysis. Figure 10. Example of susceptibility indicator related to rain intensity. Indicators can be integrated into an overall index that can finally be used for risk evaluation. As mentioned before, the outcome of the overall methodology presented in this paper is resilience building, i.e. reduction of risk. Risk mitigation for engineering infrastructure stems from the ability to appropriately evaluate critical scenarios (Figure 9). Utilizing hazard mapping alongside meteorological data enables the prediction of the intensity for specific climate factors, such as elevated rain intensity, temperatures or high winds. On the other, the determination of multiple susceptibility indicators, aggregated into an index, contribute to characterise the intrinsic conditions of the construction that make it prone to damage. Finally, by identifying the most vulnerable areas and understanding hazard trends, targeted measures can be implemented to enhance resilience.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The primary aim of the methodology presented in this research is to enhance the resilience of engineering infrastructure by accurately evaluating critical scenarios. To achieve this, an experimental approach utilizing wind tunnel simulations is proposed, enabling the characterization of risk-prone conditions through specific indicators. These indicators are derived from assessing how constructions and materials respond to various weather factors, identifying critical areas around structures, and evaluating potential mitigation measures. This study employs the Vincenc Strouhal climatic tunnel to investigate the response of building materials to rain loads, a critical factor in identifying conditions that may lead to structural damage. Such scenarios include excessive rain infiltration into deeper layers of materials, which can elevate risks of salt crystallization and freeze-thaw damage, as well as substantial surface runoff that exposes lower structural areas to prolonged moisture. Additional to climate simulation, aerodynamic testing in wind tunnels (including pressure testing and flow visualization) also plays a crucial role in examining how buildings behave under controlled airflow conditions. The results of these tests enhance understanding of wind interactions with structures, identify areas prone to damage (e.g., pollution deposition caused by vortices and turbulence), and inform strategies for improving structural resilience. Furthermore, these experiments generate fundamental data to define scenarios where constructions are particularly sensitive to climate-induced damage. The research is ongoing, with outcomes expected to include collaborative efforts among international institutions and the

development of practical resources such as guidelines, booklets, and digital tools like databases and libraries. Validation of the proposed methodologies will be achieved through case studies in partnership with industry stakeholders, ensuring that project outputs are applicable in real-world scenarios. The authors would like to acknowledge the support to this research of the INODIN project, no. CZ.02.01.01/00/23_020/0008487 of the Johannes Amos Comenius programme (OP JAK) and the GACR project number 22-08786S of the Czech Science Foundation.

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